

An Optimized Polymeric Delivery System for *piggyBac* Transposition

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Abstract

The *piggyBac* transposon/transposase system has been explored for long-term, stable gene expression to execute genomic integration of therapeutic genes, thus emerging as a strong alternative to viral transduction. Most studies with *piggyBac* transposition have employed physical methods for successful delivery of the necessary components of the *piggyBac* system into the cells. Very few studies have explored polymeric gene delivery systems. In this short communication, we report an effective delivery system based on low molecular polyethylenimine polymer with lipid substitution (PEI-L) capable of delivering three components, (i) a *piggyBac* transposon plasmid DNA carrying a gene encoding green fluorescence protein (PB-GFP), (ii) a *piggyBac* transposase plasmid DNA or mRNA and (iii) a 2 kDa polyacrylic acid as additive for transfection enhancement, all in a single complex. We demonstrate an optimized formulation for stable GFP expression in two model cell lines, MDA-MB-231 and SUM149 recorded till day 108 (3.5 months) and day 43 (1.4 months) respectively following a single treatment with very low cell number as starting material. Moreover, the stability of the transgene (GFP) expression mediated by *piggyBac*/PEI-L transposition was retained following three consecutive cryopreservation cycles. The success of this study highlights the feasibility and potential of employing a polymeric delivery system to obtain *piggyBac*-based stable expression of therapeutic genes.

INTRODUCTION

Gene transfer to correct the diseases caused by a faulty gene is the main goal of gene therapy. This can be accomplished by several approaches, including (i) introduction of a normal gene using viral vectors (Herzog *et al.*, 1997) or delivery of plasmid DNA (pDNA) (Jiang D *et al.*, 2020), and messenger RNA (Billingsley *et al.*, 2020) encoding the therapeutic gene, (ii) knockdown of the faulty gene by neutralizing the gene's mRNA using RNA Interference (RNAi) (Kristen *et al.*, 2019), and (iii) complete knockout or replacement of the target gene using CRISPR-based approach (Baylis *et al.*, 2017). These groundbreaking mechanisms have evolved over the years to achieve improved therapeutic outcomes in patients. The introduction and stable expression of a normal (therapeutic) gene is warranted in a plethora of disease conditions such as Niemann-Pick C1 (NPC1), a congenital neurodegenerative disorder that requires stable NPC1 gene expression (Kurokawa *et al.*, 2021), hemophilia B warranting F.IX expression (Herzog *et al.*, 1997), ND4 gene expression for Leber's hereditary optic neuropathy (LHON) disease that leads to blindness (Yang *et al.*, 2016), dysferlinopathy treatment in skeletal muscles through DYSF gene expression (Yakovlev *et al.*, 2023), BMP-2 expression for calvarial bone regeneration (Zhu *et al.*, 2011) and for cancer treatment through CAR-T therapy towards CD19^{+ve} malignancies (MacLeod *et al.*, 2017; Nawaz *et al.*, 2021). The aim of achieving stable expression of a therapeutic gene can be achieved mostly through genomic integration to ensure the passing down of the gene to the dividing sister cells. The genomic integration ability of viruses has been successfully harnessed to develop gene therapies capable of accomplishing stable expression of genes. Lentiviruses and retroviruses are two leading systems for viral gene transduction (Lundstrom., 2023). However, they still exhibit the risk of eliciting immune activation, and random insertional mutagenesis (Thomas *et al.*, 2003).

Alternatively, the identification of gene transposons like *piggyBac* (PB) from cabbage looper moth *Trichoplusia ni* (Cary *et al.*, 1989), *Sleeping Beauty* (SB) from Salmonid fish (Ivics *et al.*, 1997) and *Tol2* from medaka fish *Oryzias latipes* (Koga *et al.*, 1996) has proved the possibility to achieve stable gene expression using non-viral methods. Their ability to mobilize between different locations in the genome has been harnessed for a wide range of applications (Vargas *et al.*, 2016). A comparative study of these three systems revealed the higher transposition efficacy of the *piggyBac* transposons in addition to being cost effective, ability to carry a large cargo and to be able to result in functional fusion proteins (Balasubramanian *et al.*, 2016; Kaštánková *et al.*, 2021; Yusa *et al.*, 2011). Like other transposition systems, *piggyBac* consists of two main components: a donor DNA transposon pDNA designed to carry the gene of interest with the two inverted terminal repeats (ITR) and a transposase enzyme encoding pDNA (or mRNA). The synthesis of *piggyBac* transposase catalyzes the 'cut' and 'paste' mechanism (**Figure 1**). To

date, *piggyBac* has been delivered into the mammalian cells for therapeutic purposes predominantly using electroporation whose *in vivo* applicability is limited and only few studies using other non-viral methods like cationic lipids, and certain high molecular weight (HMW) polyethylenimine (PEI) polymers has been explored (Wilber *et al.*, 2007; Manuri *et al.*, 2010; Nakamura *et al.*, 2021; Magnani *et al.*, 2016; Bishop *et al.*, 2020; Ptáčková *et al.*, 2018; Qi *et al.*, 2017; Wu *et al.*, 2006; Balasubramanian *et al.*, 2016; Bire *et al.*, 2013). The HMW polymers are generally known to be toxic and there is a need for alternate non-viral methods to carry out successful transposition with minimal cellular toxicity.

We have previously established safe low molecular weight (LMW) PEI polymers with lipid substitutions (PEI-L) for different indications, such as breast cancer, acute lymphoblastic leukemia, chronic myeloid leukemia, and bone regeneration (Meenakshi Sundaram *et al.*, 2021; Thapa B *et al.*, 2019; Valencia-Serna *et al.*, 2019; Tsekoura *et al.*, 2021). Given the success of these LMW PEI-L, the aim of this report was to broaden its applicability to fulfill the unmet needs in *piggyBac* delivery as an alternate non-viral delivery system with the advantage of being a low molecular weight PEI, and low toxicity along with high transfection efficiency. *PiggyBac* pDNA transposon carrying the reporter gene green fluorescence protein (PB-GFP) and the transposase encoding pDNA (hyPBase) was designed and synthesized using a commercial vendor. In addition to carrying PB-GFP and hyPBase, polyacrylic acid (PAA) was included in the complex preparation as the introduction of such an additive improved the nucleic acid delivery efficiency (Parmar *et al.*, 2018). We explored various weight ratios of polymer to weight of the cargo containing the three components PB-GFP, hyPBase and PAA to optimize and identify the best ratio in two model cell lines over varying periods of time. We also examined the benefit of delivering the transposase as a pDNA (hyPBase) and as an mRNA. Finally, we have successfully devised and optimized an alternate *piggyBac* delivery system based on LMW PEI-L with GFP as a reporter gene which can be replaced with the gene of interest according to the needs of the researchers for long-term gene expression and for establishment of a cell line with stable gene expression.

MATERIALS and METHODS

Materials

The PAA with 2 kDa MW, DMSO (anhydrous dimethyl sulfoxide), and formaldehyde solution were procured from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO). The LMW native 1.2 kDa polyethylenimine (PEI) was from Polysciences Inc. (Warrington, PA) and synthesis of lipid-substituted PEI (PEI-L) was described previously (Tsekoura *et al.*, 2021). DMEM/F-12 (Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium/Nutrient Mixture F-12), HBSS (Hank's Balanced Salt Solution), trypsin/EDTA (Ethylene-diamine-tetra-acetic acid), penicillin,

streptomycin, and UltraPure DNase/RNase-free dH₂O were from Fisher Scientific (Ottawa, Canada). FBS (Fetal bovine serum) was from VWR Life Science Seradigm (Mississauga, Canada). *PiggyBac*-green fluorescence protein (PB-GFP), and hyperactive *piggyBac* transposase pDNA (hyPB_{ase}) were designed and synthesized from VectorBuilder (Chicago, IL) (**Figure 1A and B**). Hyperactive *piggyBac* transposase encoding mRNA was synthesized *in vitro* using T7 RNA polymerase-mediated transcription from a linearized DNA template, which incorporates the 5' and 3' UTRs and a poly-A tail as previously described (Richner *et al.*, 2017). RNA was purified using Ambion MEGA clear spin columns and then treated with Antarctic Phosphatase (New England Biolabs) for 30 min at 37°C to remove residual 5'-phosphates. Treated RNA was re-purified and quantified by Nanodrop one (Thermo Scientific). After purification, modRNA was resuspended in 10 mM Tris HCl, 1 mM EDTA at 1 µg/µl for use. In mRNA, uridine was fully replaced by N1-methylpseudouridine. In mRNA, uridine was fully replaced by N1-methylpseudouridine.

Cell Models

Metastatic breast cancer cell lines, MDA-MB-231 was gifted by Dr. Judith Hugh (Faculty of Medicine and Dentistry, University of Alberta, Edmonton) and SUM-149 was from Dr. Afsaneh Lavasanifar (Faculty of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Alberta). Cells were cultivated in DMEM/F-12 supplemented with 10% FBS, 100 U/mL penicillin, and 100 µg/mL streptomycin till they reached 80% confluency at 37°C with 5% CO₂. 0.05% trypsin/EDTA was used to collect the cells and seeded 24 hours prior to transfection.

Complex Preparation and Transfection

Complexes were prepared in serum free DMEM/F-12 by mixing pDNA with PAA followed by PEI-L addition and incubated at room temperature for 30 min. Various weight/weight ratios of polymer to pDNA/mRNA with and without PAA additive were prepared as mentioned in each treatment condition table.

Flow cytometry and Microscopy Analysis

Following the transfection of MDA-MB-231 and SUM149 cells with complexes, cells were washed with HBSS followed by 0.05% trypsin addition and incubated at 37°C incubator for 2 min and collected by adding complete DMEM/F-12 media. Following which cells were centrifuged at 1600 rpm for 5 min and fixed with 2% formaldehyde solution and analyzed with BD LSRFortessa (Becton-Dickinson, San Jose, USA) at the University of Alberta Flow Cytometry Facility. Cells without any treatment were designated as 1% GFP positive population and the mean fluorescence intensity was documented. Prior to flow cytometry processing, cells were imaged under a fluorescence microscope.

Sorting and Repeated Freeze/Thaw Analysis

Following 37 days of SUM149-GFP culturing, cells were sorted to attain a pure population of GFP modified cells using Sony MA900 Multi-Application Cell Sorter at the University of Alberta Flow Cytometry Facility. Cells were then frozen using 5% DMSO freezing medium on day 66. After 216 days, cells were thawed and analyzed by flow cytometry for GFP cells, this was repeated on day 219 and day 221 for a total of 3 repeated free/thaw cycles consecutively.

Statistical Analysis

Results were summarized as mean \pm standard deviation and the unpaired Student's *t*-test employed to denote the statistical difference between the group mean. Significance was determined in comparison with the control groups as explained in the respective figure legends.

RESULTS

Polymeric Delivery of pDNA and mRNA transposase in MDA-MB-231 Cells

The transposase enzyme required for the 'cut' and 'paste' of the GFP DNA transposon (**Figure 1A**) onto the genomic DNA can be delivered as (i) a pDNA (**Figure 1B**) which would then lead to the synthesis of mRNA transposase followed by production of the transposase enzyme or (ii) as a mRNA transposase, which can immediately start the synthesis of transposase enzyme (**Figure 1C**).

Figure 1: *PiggyBac* mediated GFP gene transfer. A schematic representation of the two components (A) *piggyBac*-GFP transposon plasmid and (B) *piggyBac* transposase plasmid with (C) the mechanism of 'cut' and 'paste' of the GFP gene into the genomic DNA.

Six different treatment conditions were employed to compare the efficacy of pDNA and mRNA mediated-transposase activity. The amount of transposase expression system (whether hyPBBase pDNA or mRNA) was kept constant at 0.25 μg while the amount of GFP DNA transposon (PB-GFP) varied from 0.125 to 4 μg achieving the PB-GFP to transposase weight by weight ratios of 0.5:1, 1:1, 2:1, 4:1, 8:1 and 16:1 labelled as Group 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 8 and 16 as mentioned (**Figure 2A**). The ratio of the additive PAA to PB-GFP was kept constant at 1, which was selected as the best ratio based on a preliminary study. As outlined in the scheme (**Figure 2B**), 24 hours prior to treatment, MDA-MB-231 cells were seeded, and a single transfection was carried out with the 6 different conditions/ratios. Following which GFP positive cells were

passed and analyzed by recording fluorescence microscopy images, flow cytometry analysis and re-seeded on days 10, 18, 25, 39, 48, 56, 64, 76, 90 and 108 to assess the extent of stable GFP expression among the treatment groups over long periods.

Figure 2: (A) A summary of the various weight/weight ratios between the PB-GFP and transposase (hyPBBase or mRNA) with the corresponding varying amounts of PB-GFP (μg) and a constant amount of transposase either as plasmid hyPBBase (μg) or mRNA (μg). **(B)** Schematic overview of the sequence of the study with the initial seeding of MDA-MB-231 cells (day -1) followed by treatment after 24 hours (day 0) and subsequent passaging with simultaneous analysis by flow cytometry, microscopy, and re-seeding at various time points till day 108.

With PB-GFP treatment group (without transposase), the initial percentage of GFP-positive cells on day 10 was between 5% to >10% (**Figure 3A**) while the mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) was between 350 to 549 (**Figure 3B**). With increase in time, both GFP-positive cell percentage as well as the MFI decreased and was completely lost by day 48, denoting the lack of genomic integration of the GFP gene in the absence of the transposase enzyme. Treatment Group 16 (**Figure 2A**) exhibited sustained percentage of GFP-positive cells until day 39 with very low MFI which can be attributed to the high amount of PB-GFP (4 μg) present, which was followed by Groups 8 and 4 indicating a concentration dependent effect of GFP expression in the cells.

Figure 3: GFP expression in MDA-MB-231 cell line till day 108 following a single treatment with PB-GFP alone or PB-GFP+hyPBase pDNA or PB-GFP+mRNA PBase in the presence of PAA additive. **(A)** Heat map showing the percentage of GFP-positive cells. **(B)** MFI of the total population. **(C)** Representative fluorescence microscopic images for the successful groups 4:1 and 8:1. Statistically significant differences

are denoted by bold rectangle for the specific treatment groups compared to the respective PB-GFP alone groups (without transposase) in the heatmap with $P < 0.02$, $N = 2$.

With PB-GFP + hyPBBase pDNA group, the GFP-positive cells were between 5% to >10% (**Figure 3A**) on day 10. Groups 2 and 4 exhibited approximately similar extent of sustained GFP expression till day 76 reflected in both percentage of GFP-positive cells and MFI (**Figure 3B**); however, at day 90 and 108, Group 2 lost the cells that were modified with GFP. Group 4 emerged as the most promising treatment ratio as the GFP-positive percentage was between 5% to 10% with MFI of 350 to 549 among all other treatment conditions. Groups 8 and 16 had a high percentage of GFP cells till day 39 but Group 16 lost the treatment effect over time, whereas Group 8 was the second successful treatment condition following Group 4. Group 8 had 5% to 10% GFP cells with MFI >550 on day 76, however by day 108 the modified cells were lost completely.

With PB-GFP + mRNA PBase group, a similar trend of high GFP modified cells was observed at lower timepoints of day 10 to 25 with Groups 2 to 16 (**Figure 3A**). Like the hyPBBase group, Groups 2 and 4 were the best treatment conditions, with Group 4 exhibiting the highest efficacy till day 108 with GFP-positive percentage of >10%, however the MFI was between 50 to 149 (**Figure 3B**). Moreover, considering an overall comparison on total number of positive outcomes with all the treatment groups and time points between hyPBBase and mRNA PBase on GFP-positive percentage and MFI, the hyPBBase pDNA gave a marginally higher effect compared to the mRNA PBase. Specifically, with GFP-positive percentage, there are 25 positive outcomes with hyPBBase pDNA compared to 20 with mRNA PBase and with MFI hyPBBase pDNA has 25 compared to 19 with mRNA PBase, whereas the PB-GFP without transposase has only 12 (GFP positive %) and 4 (MFI) groups that were effective. A summary of representative fluorescent images (**Figure 3C**) of groups 4 and 8 from day 4 to day 108 provides a better understanding on the effect of hyPBBase pDNA compared to mRNA PBase and without transposase (PB-GFP) treatments.

Optimization of Treatment Conditions/Formulation Ratios in SUM149 Cells

Following the better performance of hyPBBase pDNA in MDA-MB-231 at the ratio 4:1, we chose this treatment group and varied the amount of polymeric delivery system according to the components utilized in the complex preparation process. A weight/weight ratio of 5 (polymer to PAA) was employed for all the conditions as summarized in **Figure 4A**. The amount of polymer was calculated with respect to the components in the square brackets [] mentioned in **Figure 4A** conditions. For Group 2, the polymer amount was 5 times the weight of PB-GFP (no PAA was used), whereas for Group 3 the polymer was 5 times the weight of PB-GFP and PAA. A similar method of calculation was followed for the rest of the

groups. The primary aim of this study was to determine the amount of polymer required for optimal performance of the complexes that carry all three components PB-GFP, PAA (additive) and hyPBase pDNA.

Figure 4: (A) A summary of the various treatment conditions/ weight ratios between the PB-GFP, hyPBase, PAA and the PEI-L polymer. Values in the brackets [] represent the sum of the weights considered while calculating the weight of PEI-L which was kept constant at a ratio of 5. **(B)** Schematic overview of the sequence of the study with the initial seeding of SUM149 cells (day -1) followed by treatment after 24 hours (day 0) and subsequent passaging with simultaneous analysis by flow cytometry, microscopy, and re-seeding at various time points till day 43.

As summarized in **Figure 4B**, cells were seeded 24 hours prior to the treatment, after which a single transfection was carried out. Cells were collected and analyzed for GFP expression on day 2, 13, 23 and 43 through microscopic and flow cytometric assays. 2 days post treatment, groups 3, 5, 6, 9 and 10 displayed very high GFP expression ranging between 77% to 84% of positive cells with MFI between 10^4 to $>4 \times 10^4$ (**Figure 5A and 5B**). The ultimate basis for the variation in polymer calculation in this study was due to the presence of 3 anionic components, PB-GFP, hyPBase pDNA and PAA. All the components must be complexed into a compact single nanoparticle for successful intracellular delivery. It is evident that to establish optimal transfection, the amount of polymer should be calculated with respect to the total amount of anionic components as observed in groups 3, 5, 6, 9 and 10. With the increase in time on day 13, 23 and 43 the transfection efficiency with group 3 (without transposase) declined as reflected on

percentage of GFP-positive cells and MFI (Figure 5A and 5B). Conversely, we could see ~10% GFP-positive cells along with high MFI of $\sim 10^4$ with Groups 5, 6, 9 and 10 till day 43 which showcases the stable integration of GFP gene into 10% of SUM149 cell line which can also be confirmed with representative fluorescence images from day 2 and day 43 (Figure 5C).

Groups such as 7, 8, 11 and 12 showed ~5% to ~30% on day 2, which was lower compared to the GFP-positive cells for other groups and the transfection efficiency declined (for groups 7, 8, 11 and 12) to ~5% to ~9% with very low MFI equivalent to NT on day 43, even though hyPBase pDNA was also included in the complex preparation process. The low transfection efficiency with these treatment groups is possibly due to improper complexation as low amount of polymers were added in these groups therefore improper transfection and presumably lack of gene integration.

Figure 5: GFP expression in SUM149 cell line from day 2 to day 43 following a single treatment with PB-GFP + hyPBase pDNA at varying ratios. **(A)** Histogram showing the GFP-positive cells. **(B)** Heat map showing the MFI of the total population. **(C)** Representative fluorescence microscopic images on day 2 and day 43. Statistically significant differences are denoted by bold rectangle for the specific treatment groups on day 48 compared to group 3 (without transposase) in the heatmap with $P < 0.01$, $N = 2$.

Effect of Repeated Cryopreservation on Stable GFP expression in SUM149 Cells

The cells in the successful treatment Groups 5, 9 and 10 were sorted to collect a pure population of GFP-positive cells on day 37 and were allowed to divide further and frozen for future studies on day 66 (**Figure 6A-C**). After 150 days of being frozen in 5% DMSO, these samples were thawed on day 216 since its initial transfection. We intended to evaluate the impact of freeze-thaw on the GFP expression attained by transposon/transposase system in SUM149 cells established by our polymeric system, as repeated cryopreservation involving freeze-thaw cycle could affect the expression of the inserted gene in the modified cells. The thawed cells were allowed to divide for 48 hours and the percentage of GFP cells and the MFI was evaluated through flow cytometry analysis and the findings were plotted as initial time point values (**Figure 7A-C**). Following which, the same cells underwent three freeze-thaw cycles with ~48 hours of interval providing time for the cells to recover before flow cytometry analysis. The percentage of GFP-positive cells, MFI and the fluorescence of the GFP-positive cells was calculated with no treatment set at 1% as a background of GFP-positive cells.

Figure 6: Fluorescence microscopic images of GFP-modified sorted SUM149 cells for the treatments **(A)** Group 5 [1:1:0.25]:5, **(B)** Group 9 [1:1.25:0.25]:5, **(C)** Group 10 [1:2:1]:5 of [PB-GFP:PAA:hyPBBase]:Pol.

The initial percentage of GFP-positive cells for Groups 5, 9 and 10 were ~40%, ~50% and ~40% respectively (**Figure 7A**). Following 3 freeze-thaw cycles a slight decrease can be observed, however it remained stable over the three time points frozen at ~25%, ~40% and ~20% (for Groups 5, 9 and 10). A similar decrease was seen with MFI from the initial to first frozen time point (3 days) but remained steady at second (7 days) and third (12 days) time points for Groups 5 and 9 but not with Group 10 (**Figure 7B**). With the fluorescence of GFP-positive population, the values remained same between the initial and first frozen time point (3 days) and a sharp decrease can be seen at second time point with the values remaining stable at the third frozen time point. This was applicable to all the 3 groups but to a different extent as Group 5 exhibited higher fluorescence values (3000 to 2000) than Groups 9 and 10 (2500 to 1000). Overall, the modification established by Groups 5 and 9 appeared to be more stable compared to

Group 10 (**Figure 7C**). Subjecting the GFP transposon modified cells to repeated freeze-thaw cycles does alter the gene expression to a lesser degree, but we were able to sustain the effect as the GFP modified cells remained stable even after 3 freeze-cycles performed over a period of 12 days.

Figure 7: Flow cytometric analysis showing (A) GFP-positive population, (B) MFI and (C) fluorescence intensity of GFP-positive cells at the initial time point, and after 3 freeze thaw cycles for the successful treatment Groups 5, 9 and 10 in SUM149 cell line. * $P < 0.05$, $N = 2$.

DISCUSSION

The discovery of transposons, capable of achieving genomic integration efficacy close to the viral systems (Lin *et al.*, 2022) has given hope to patients who require lifelong gene expression without the risks associated with viral systems. The integration ability of the *piggyBac* transposon with the aid of *piggyBac* transposase to recognize ('cut') the inverted terminal repeats (ITR) and its integration ('paste') into the genome ensures long-term gene expression with non-random insertion. Specifically, *piggyBac* widely prefers integration near transcriptional start sites (TSS), and CpG islands 50% of the time, especially towards the TTAA regions in the human genome, making it easier for predictability (Yusa *et al.*, 2011; Galvan *et al.*, 2009). The development of a hyperactive *piggyBac* transposase (hyPBBase) which improved the transposition efficiency by 10-fold in mouse ES cells, 293T and NIH 3T3 cells (Yusa *et al.*, 2011) has been employed in this study.

Like any nucleic acid-based therapeutics, the successful therapeutic outcome is dependent on the efficiency of the delivery system used. Since the *piggyBac* transposons are plasmid-based which are delivered along with a transposase sourced as either a pDNA or mRNA, it is imperative that the delivery system employed can effectively deliver two nucleic acids with minimal toxicity. Most of the successful transposon studies have utilized electroporation-based approach. A *Sleeping Beauty* transposon system was utilized to successfully develop human embryonic stem cells (ESC) with stable GFP or luciferase gene expression to understand the therapeutic potential of these cells, with luciferase expression recorded till 5 months (~150 days). However, this was established using nucleofection employing a high amount (10 µg) of transposon pDNA and 5 µg transposase pDNA or RNA (Wilber *et al.*, 2007). Another study utilizing *piggyBac* system developed CD19-specific CAR T-cells by delivering CD19RCD28 encoding *PB* transposon and *PB* transposase for targeted killing of B-lineage malignancies; however, this was possible utilizing 7.5 µg of the transposon pDNA and 7.5 µg transposase pDNA (15 µg total pDNA) through nucleofection (Manuri *et al.*, 2010). Similarly, HER2-, CD19- and GD2-CAR-T cells were generated with 5 µg of the transposon pDNA and 7.5 µg of transposase pDNA which was also delivered by nucleofection to attain CAR-T cells with anti-tumor activity (Nakamura *et al.*, 2021). 15 µg of CD19-CAR or GFP-encoding transposon pDNA and 5 µg of transposase pDNA were delivered by nucleofection to produce CAR-T cells against CD19 positive acute myelogenous leukemia (AML) and acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) with a stable CAR expression till day 21 (Magnani *et al.*, 2016). As summarized in **Table 1**, various other successful studies also used nucleofection or electroporation-based approach for the delivery of plasmids into the cells at amounts ranging between 0.6 µg to 40 µg for stable gene expression, which was monitored for 7 to 24 days post treatment (Bishop *et al.*, 2020; Ptáčková *et al.*, 2018; Qi *et al.*, 2017; Yusa *et al.*, 2011). Although such approaches are successful in developing cells with stable gene expression, its clinical translation is plagued with challenges such as the need for an electroporation equipment, low cell viability due to the electricity applied, and optimization of treatment conditions according to the cell type (Lee *et al.*, 2009). Most importantly, the collection, isolation, modification, expansion, and reinfusion of the patient cells under aseptic conditions using specialized instruments is an expensive approach (Harris *et al.*, 2021).

Alternative methods of delivery involving cationic lipids and polymer-based systems have also been explored, such as jetPEI™, TransMessenger™, TransIT®mRNA and FuGENE®6, but have been used only to study the internalization and trafficking mechanism of mRNA based *piggyBac* transposase and to compare the transposition efficiency of different transposon systems (Bire *et al.*, 2013; Wu *et al.*, 2006). High MW PEI (25 kDa linear PEI) was used for delivering of 22.5 µg of pDNA mixed with 45 µg of PEI in

CHO-DG44 cell line comparing the transposon systems *piggyBac*, *Tol2* and *Sleeping Beauty* (Balasubramanian *et al.*, 2016). The key drawback of high MW delivery systems is the associated toxicity which in turn affects the clinical translation (Godbey *et al.*, 1999). Therefore, we have utilized low MW PEI with lipid substitution (PEI-L) to accomplish a safe and effective *piggyBac* delivery system capable of achieving stable GFP expression. PAA was included to increase the delivery efficiency, as observed in our previous studies. Additionally, PEI-L used in this study exhibited low toxicity (80 to 100% cell viability under transfection conditions) as reported previously by Parmar *et al.*, 2018, Thapa *et al.*, 2019, Aliabadi *et al.*, 2020; Santadkha *et al.*, 2022 in published studies with breast cancer cell lines.

	Delivery Agent	Transposon	Transposase	Cells	Duration	Ref.
1	Nucleofection	<i>SB</i> : GFP or Luc	pDNA/mRNA	Human - ESC	5 mon	Wilber <i>et al.</i> , 2007
2	Nucleofection	<i>PB</i> : CD19-CAR	pDNA	T cells	n/a	Manuri <i>et al.</i> , 2010
3	Nucleofection	<i>PB</i> : CAR-CD19 HER2, GD2	pDNA	T cells	n/a	Nakamura <i>et al.</i> , 2021
4	Nucleofection	<i>SB</i> : CD19-CAR or GFP	pDNA	T cells	21 days	Magnani <i>et al.</i> , 2016
5	Electroporation	<i>PB</i> : CD19-CAR	pDNA	T cells	15 days	Bishop <i>et al.</i> , 2020
6	Electroporation	<i>PB</i> : CD19-CAR	pDNA	T cells	24 days	Ptáčková <i>et al.</i> , 2018
7	Electroporation	<i>PB</i> : various genes	pDNA	Mouse ESC HCT116, HEK293T	7 days	Qi <i>et al.</i> , 2017
8	Electroporation	<i>piggyBac</i> : various genes	pDN/mRNA	293T, NIH 3T3 Mouse ESC	n/a	Yusa <i>et al.</i> , 2011
9	FUGENE®6	<i>PB</i> , <i>SB</i> , <i>Tol2</i> , <i>Mos1</i> : <i>hygromycin</i>	pDNA	CHO, HeLa H1299 HEK293	14 days	Wu <i>et al.</i> , 2006
10	Linear 25 kDa PEI	<i>PB</i> , <i>Tol2</i> , <i>SB</i>	pDNA	CHO-DG44	2 mon	Balasubramanian <i>et al.</i> , 2016
11	jetPEI™, Trans- Messenger™ TransIT®mRNA	<i>piggyBac</i> : GFP or V5PB	pDNA/mRNA	HeLa	n/a	Bire <i>et al.</i> , 2013

Table 1: Summary of studies on transposon delivery, indicating the delivery agents, transposon type, transposase delivery method, cell type and duration of the study post treatment. *SB* = *Sleeping Beauty*, *PB* = *piggyBac*.

In addition to the delivery system, another key factor governing the success of gene expression using pDNA is the promoter selection, which influences the duration and level of protein expression (Gill

et al., 2009). The GFP gene in the PB-GFP plasmid was regulated by human cytomegalovirus immediate early enhancer/promoter (CMV) whereas the transposase in hyPBase plasmid was regulated by elongation factor-1 α (EF1A) promoter as shown in **Figure 1**, given their superior performance in previous reports (Rad *et al.*, 2020; Wang *et al.*, 2016). The mRNA transposase was synthesized using the hyPBase plasmid sequence. Use of mRNA transposase was expected to be advantageous compared to the pDNA counterpart, as it would ensure high gene expression in a short period, which could be sufficient to initiate transposition followed by the degradation of mRNA (Bire *et al.*, 2013), leaving less of a footprint compared to the pDNA.

The ratio of the transposon pDNA to transposase pDNA or mRNA is another contributing factor towards the success of genomic integration of gene of interest. Since transposase catalyzes the process of transposition, the amount of transposase plays an important role in the overall success of integration as low production can reduce the transposition effect. Hence it is important to optimize the ratio of transposon/transposase (Tipanee *et al.*, 2017). Previous reports utilized ratios ranging from 1:1 to 9:1 (transposon:transposase) among different delivery agents (**Table 1**). The amounts ranged from 0.05 μ g to 15 μ g. Due to this huge variation among previous reports, we evaluated the GFP expression with complexes prepared at different PB-GFP:hyPBase or mRNA transposase ratios along with varying amounts of transposon pDNA (PB-GFP) for PEI-L delivery system. We identified ratio 4:1 containing 1 μ g of PB-GFP with 0.25 μ g of hyPBase to be more efficient followed by ratio 8:1 having 2 μ g of PB-GFP with 0.25 μ g hyPBase for long term GFP expression in MDA-MB-231 cells. This was also true in mRNA transposase group with ratio 4:1, however the effect was less pronounced on day 108 especially with MFI but not in GFP-positive cell population. This difference in high GFP-positive cells but low MFI, could be explained as high percentage of cells undergoing GFP gene transposition, but the extent of integration being lower denoted by a low MFI. The reason for the gradual loss of GFP MFI from day 76 to day 108 observed only with mRNA transposase (unlike hyPBase pDNA) at ratio 4:1, has not been explored in this study. Conversely, the treatment with hyPBase group at 4:1 saw an increase in GFP expression from day 76 to day 108 (both in GFP-positive cell population and MFI), possibly due to a more stable genomic integration with dividing cells being able to carry the GFP gene. The other ratios containing high (0.5:1, 1:1 and 2:1) as well as low (16:1) transposase amount did not exhibit long-term GFP expression which can be attributed to over- or under-production of transposase enzyme which in turn resulted in unsuccessful transposition (Tipanee *et al.*, 2017). This confirms the crucial role of transposase amount for successful transpositions.

The principle behind the complexation between the cationic PEI-L and anionic nucleic acids is electrostatic interactions. Since our complexes contained three anionic components, (i) PB-GFP (7188 bp),

(ii) hypBase pDNA (7510 bp) or mRNA transposase (1785 bases) and (iii) PAA (2 kDa), it was essential to identify the optimal ratio of PEI-L required to complex all three components. This was pursued here in SUM149 cells at 4:1 transposon to transposase ratio which was an ideal combination for effective transposition/genomic integration. Based on the long-term GFP expression outcomes, the 11 different treatment conditions from Groups (2) to (12) summarized in **Figure 4A**, can be divided into two sections with conditions in Groups 5/6/9/10 having higher PEI-L amount and conditions in Groups 7/8/11/12 having lower PEI-L amount. The higher PEI-L amount led to sustained GFP expression till day 43 in which the weight of PEI-L was calculated towards the total weight of PB-GFP, PAA and hypBase. Whereas with the lower PEI-L amount groups, the MFI was lost by day 43 as the weight of PEI-L was calculated with respect to total weight of PB-GFP and hypBase without the consideration of PAA weight. From this study, it was evident that the weight of PEI-L calculated for complex preparation should include the total weight of the anionic components to reach superior transfection efficiency. This observation aligned with the findings by Santadkha *et al.*, 2022 using siRNA complexes, where the weight of the transfection reagent calculated to the sum of siRNA and additive helped in therapeutic outcome with breast cancer cells.

The observed long-term expression of GFP in both cell lines can be attributed to genomic integration of the transgene. Although this has not been validated in this study, previous findings by Hamada *et al.*, 2018 using *piggyBac* transposition for CD19 CAR transgene has confirmed the integration through genome-wide insertion mapping studies in T cells. Similarly, Meir *et al.*, 2011 and Galvan *et al.*, 2009 also confirmed the genomic transposition through chromosomal transposition assay in HEK293 and T cells, all of which support the genomic integration ability of *piggyBac* systems. The loss of GFP expression could be the result of failure of transgene integration with the PB-GFP alone treatment (without transposase), as PB-GFP could get diluted with cell replication, resulting in eventual disappearance of the plasmid that corresponds to the decline of GFP expression (Mulia *et al.*, 2021). On the contrary, the treatment groups containing transposase prolonged the GFP expression possibly due to genomic integration. Another factor is the effect of epigenetic silencing due to the persistence of the transposase DNA leading to silencing instead of transposition in the groups containing high transposase quantity. Efforts have been made to address this through the inclusion of insulators which are DNA regulatory elements with the property to prevent this scenario (Bire *et al.*, 2013). Reduced proliferation of the modified cells could be another factor for the long-term GFP expression compared to control groups, although the cells underwent frequent subculturing in our study, thereby replenishing the growth media and providing space for the cells to grow (Meir *et al.*, 2011). Furthermore, insertional mutagenesis with *piggyBac* is possible, as a study conducted by Yusa *et al.*, 2011 revealed a 0.2% frequency of excision

events leading to excision-induced mutations which was very low compared to the earlier reports of 5-10% with piggyBac systems. It was also concluded that the hyPBase used in our study exhibited the transposition without altering the genomic integrity. Similarly, Meir *et al.*, 2011 reported the ability of *piggyBac* transposons to implement only a few copies of the transgene insertion thereby reducing insertional mutagenesis which was also shown by Galvan *et al.*, 2009 through a genome-wide study.

Having optimized and shown success of *piggyBac*-based sustained GFP expression in 2 cell lines using non-viral PEI-L vector, we explored the stability of integration by monitoring GFP expression after repeated cryopreservation. Cryopreservation is a common method to store cells for future use, which should not elicit any change in gene expression. Previous studies with lentiviral transduced CD34⁺ cells with globin gene expression did not exhibit any difference following 2 freeze/thaw cycles (Karponi *et al.*, 2018). A similar observation was noted with electroporation-based modification of NS0 cells (Barnes *et al.*, 2003). Accordingly, we also investigated the performance of *piggyBac*/PEI-L method of modified SUM149 cells to three repeated freeze/thaw cycles. For this purpose, GFP-positive SUM149 cells were sorted, which represented the initial (baseline) data (time point) for GFP-positive population and MFI. Although we noticed a slight decrease in GFP-positive population as well as MFI after the first freeze/thaw cycle, we did not observe any further decrease after that. In the cryopreservation studies with CD34⁺ cells (Karponi *et al.*, 2018), no difference in protein expression was observed, but a 40% decrease in the clonogenic capacity was recorded following freeze/thaw showing an effect of cryopreservation. Altogether, this is the first study to explore the effect of repeated cryopreservation on the gene expression mediated by *piggyBac*-based genomic transposition delivered. Additionally, we achieved stable GFP expression in both MDA-MB-231 and SUM149 cells with starting relatively cell numbers at 12×10^3 cells and 6×10^4 cells respectively, which are much lower compared to previous reports. This indicates that a small population of cells might be sufficient to obtain modified cells and cells from rare sources could be employed with the transposition method described here. The clinical success of *piggyBac* transposon is mostly focused on CAR-T cells generated towards (i) epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) CAR-T cells for advanced relapsed non-small cell lung cancer patients in a phase I clinical trial (Zhang *et al.*, 2021), (ii) CD19 CAR-T cells for relapsed B-cell malignancy in a phase I clinical trial (Micklethwaite *et al.*, 2021) and (iii) CD116 also known as GM-CSF receptor alpha chain (GMR) CAR-T cells towards relapsed myeloid malignancies in a phase I/II study (Saito *et al.*, 2021). All these *piggyBac*-based stable gene expressions were established through electroporation of T-cells. We propose an alternate method of effectively delivering the transposon system and it will be interesting to validate the effectiveness on the long-term expression of therapeutic proteins by this *piggyBac*/PEI-L system.

In conclusion, we have formulated an effective PEI-L delivery system capable of delivering the complex payload containing three components, PB-GFP, hyPBase or mRNA and PAA for prolonged expression of a model protein (GFP) in model cell lines MDA-MB-231 and SUM149 with a single treatment. We have also established a reliable system capable of maintaining the protein expression even after three consecutive cryopreservation (free/thaw) cycles, all of these were obtained with minimal starting cell numbers.

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